

Photovoltaic Water Pumping System for a Desert Area in Egypt

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ABSTRACT

This paper illustrates a study of sizing and dynamic modelling of a large scale solar powered water pumping system for irrigation in Egypt. The system is expected to deliver 500 m^3 of water per day. Sizing such a system has been carried out by using some useful tool such as PVsyst. A 130 m water level in a deep well. System dynamic modelling is done using Matlab/Simulink which contains several models of such systems such as 58 kW solar arrays, DC-DC boost converter, 54 kW DC-AC converter (Inverter), 50 hp AC motor, and centrifugal pump. In order to improve the system efficiency, perturbation and observation (P&O) algorithm based maximum power point tracker (MPPT) was built in the system model for the converter. Matlab/Simulink simulation shows that this system can deliver the required energy with quite satisfactory controller dynamic performance.

Key words: Solar powered water pumping system, DC-DC boost converter, DC-AC converter (Inverter), MPPT, Renewable Energy, PVsyst

1. INTRODUCTION

Solar powered water pumping system has been regarded as an appropriate choice for the grid-isolated countryside regions in developing and advanced countries, including Egypt, in which high amounts of solar radiation are available [1]. Solar powered water pumping systems have the ability to distribute drinking water without any type of additional power or the complicated upkeep, which, for example, require diesel pumps, as it was outlined in the report by the Department of Energy of the United States [2]. In addition, in spite of the fact that solar powered water pumping systems are not suitable for large-scale irrigation, they are able to efficiently operate in the areas with small-scale drip irrigation systems [3]. The solar powered water pumping systems could be regarded as being large-scale in a case when it serves more than two hundred and forty people. However, Photovoltaic solar panels are frequently utilized to perform various agricultural operations, in distant regions or in areas in which the utilization of an alternative energy sources is preferable [4]. To be precise, the solar powered water pumping systems have been established in the course of the last decade to consistently generate an adequate amount of electricity straight from the radiation of the sun in order to deliver water to cattles [5].

Fig. 1 Constituents of solar powered water pumping systems.

The longstanding financial expenses and the capability of solar powered water pumping system of being adjustable in accordance with the constantly altering demands has to be realized in the feasibility of this pumping system. This development is to some extent connected to the capability of the general population that utilizes the pumping system for irrigation of being able to adjust to constantly altering demands as well. According to [6], solar powered water pumping system is the one of best alternative solution for irrigation. The figure below shows the components of the solar powered water pumping system.

This paper is divided into several sections as follows: section 2 covers the description of PV water pumping system. Optimization of system sizing using PVsyst software [11] is given in section 3, System modeling description in section 4, The results will be discussed in section 5 followed by the conclusion.

2. PV WATER PUMPING SYSTEM (PVWPS) DESCRIPTION

PVWPS has been designated to be built in a shiny spot where there is noteworthy solar irradiation. This system is supplying to a farm located in Wadi El Natron, Egypt which is blessed with high intensity of sun shine, as figure 2 depicts, where it reaches $7.049 \text{ kWh/m}^2/\text{day}$ as the monthly average solar irradiation. We assumed off-grid and completely independent system and sizing using two softwares.

Fig. 2 Monthly average solar irradiation in Wadi El Natron, Egypt.

3. SOLAR WATER PUMPING SYSTEM SIZING METHODOLOGY

Fig. 3 Flowchart of solar water pumping system sizing

-Water Demand: In this study, a large-scale solar powered water pumping system has been designed for an average farm located in Wadi El Natron, Egypt. The required amount of water is estimated to be $500 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$ as an average daily demand. The layout of such system is shown below.

-Water Dynamic Head: The total head includes the distance from pump level to the tank as well as the fraction of elbows. As shown below, the total head dynamic is :

$$\text{THD} = 155 \text{ m (vertical)} + [(1.8 \times 3 \text{ elbows}) + 20 \text{ m}] \times 20\% + 4 \text{ m (vertical)} = 164.08 \text{ m}$$

Fig. 4 The layout of 500 m³/day solar powered water pumping system

4. OPTIMIZATION OF SYSTEM SIZING USING PVsyst

To start sizing such a system, the pump size is an important aspect that needs to be assessed. As the total head and water demand are known for a farm, the pump size calculation is forthright, and can be completed using the following expression.

$$P_{hyd} = \rho gHQ \quad (W) \tag{1}$$

$$P = \frac{\rho gHQ}{\eta} \tag{2}$$

Where :

ρ is the density of water (1000 kg/m³), g is the gravitational acceleration (9.81 m/s²), H is the total head (m) Q is the volumetric flow rate of water (m³/s), and η pump efficiency(80%) .

Results from equations 1, 2 show that the calculated pump size is 33.5 kW which can deliver the required amount of water.

Load has been inserted into PVsyst as shown in figure 5. It can be noticed that the pump runs for 8 hours per day from 9 am to 5 pm. The aim is to utilize it as much as possible, in daylight, particularly during the peak time from 10 am to 6 pm.

Fig. 5 Screenshot of PVsyst the simulation parameters and sizing suggestions

Figure 5 shows the parameters of the selected system in PVsyst which The PV size is 124 kW and pump size is 98.1 kW. As mentioned before, the pump size was 33.5 kW, which is not matching with suggested pump power. However, actually, we recommended the right pump to the honor, but he insisted on the small pump that he already had before.

5. SYSTEM MODELINGDESCRIPTION

A standalone 58 kW solar powered water pumping system is designed. Such system is a DC coupled consists of 176 PV modules, maximum power point tracker (MPPT), DC-DC boost converter, DC-AC Inverter and AC water pump as shown in figure 6.

Fig. 6. The block diagram of the proposed system.

5.1. Modeling of PV Module

The specifications in table 1 for a 330W PV module have been used as well as the equations 3-6 to build such module based on the equivalent circuit of solar cell shown below in figure 7.

Fig. 7 The equivalent circuit of solar cell

Table -1 Solar PV Module Specifications

Electrical Characteristics	
330 W	Rated Power
37.5 V	Voltage at Maximum power (Vmp)
8.81 A	Current at Maximum power (Imp)
46.2 V	Open circuit voltage (VOC)
9.38 A	Short circuit current (ISCr)
12	Total number of cells in series (Ns)
6	Total number of strings in parallel (Np)
45±2°C	Nominal Operating Cell Temperature (NOCT)
-0.41 %/°C	Temperature Coefficient of Pmax
-0.33 %/°C	Temperature Coefficient of Voc
0.067 %/°C	Temperature Coefficient of Isc

$$I = I_{ph} - I_{D1} - I_{D2} - \frac{V+IR_s}{R_p} \tag{3}$$

$$I_{D1} = I_{o1} \left[\exp \left(\frac{q(V+IR_s)}{akT} \right) - 1 \right] \tag{4}$$

$$I_{D1} = I_{o2} \left[\exp \left(\frac{q(V+IR_s)}{akT} \right) - 1 \right] \tag{5}$$

$$I = I_{ph} - I_o \left[\exp \left(\frac{q(V+IR_s)}{akT} \right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V+IR_s}{R_p} \tag{6}$$

5.2. Modeling of DC-DC Boost Converter

This part illustrates the design of DC-DC boost converter based on Matlab/Simulink. It helps regulating voltage of PV array to a fixed high level voltage which is going to meet the demand of 380V water pump.

Fig. 8 The block diagram of DC-DC boost converter.

$$\frac{V_{out}}{V_{in}} = \frac{t_{on} + t_{off}}{t_{off}} = \frac{1}{1-d} \quad ; \text{Where } d = \text{duty cycle} \tag{7}$$

the inductor ripple current

$$\Delta I_L = 1.75\% \times I_{out(max)} \times \frac{V_{out}}{V_{in}} \tag{8}$$

$$L = \frac{V_{in} \times (V_{out} - V_{in})}{\Delta I_L \times F_s \times V_{out}} \tag{9}$$

MPPT is commonly used to increase the efficiency of PV systems. It operates in very high frequency, usually from 20 to 80 kHz. The reason behind that is it converts DC to DC to operate PV at MPPT. High frequency circuit works as a large transformer that allows boosting voltage and current to the desirable values, thus, meeting the voltage demand of water pump and a controller.

PV voltage and current regulated to MPP by P&O algorithm as shown in figure 10 and the flow chart in figure 9.

Fig. 9 Perturbation and observation method algorithm.

Fig. 10 P&O algorithm implementation

5.3. Modeling of DC-AC Inverter

Voltage source inverters (VSI) are mainly used to convert a constant DC voltage into 3-phase AC voltages with variable magnitude and frequency. The inverter is composed of six switches S1 through S6 with each phase output connected to the middle of each “inverter leg”. Two switches in each phase are used to construct one leg. The AC output voltage from the inverter is obtained by controlling the semiconductor switches ON and OFF to generate the

desired output. Pulse width modulation (PWM) techniques are widely used to perform this task. In the simplest form, three reference signals are compared to a high frequency carrier waveform. The result of that comparison in each leg is used to turn the switches ON or OFF. This technique is referred to as sinusoidal pulse width modulation (SPWM). It should be noted that the switches in each leg should be operated interchangeably, in order not to cause a short circuit of the DC supply.

Fig. 11 The block diagram of DC-AC Inverter

5.4. Modeling AC Motor and Centrifugal Pump

A 37 kW AC motor connected to a centrifugal pump has been designed by Simulink to deliver 500 m³ of water per day.

The AC motor and pump specifications are shown in table 2.

Table- 2 Motor and Pump Specifications

AC Pump Specifications					
TYPE	Impeller	Voltage (V)	Pump Power (W)	Max Flow (m ³ /H)	Max Head (m)
GRUNDFOS - SP	Centrifugal	400	37000	60	300
AC Motor Specifications					
TYPE	Nominal Power (HP)	Voltage (V)	Frequency (Hz)	Nominal Speed (RPM)	Pole Pairs
Three Phase Induction Motor	50	400	50	2860	2

The equivalent circuit of the AC motor has been modeled in Simulink as shown in figure 12. (simscape blocks)

Fig. 12 AC motor simulation in Simulink.

6. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

6.1 Results of PVsyst Software

Fig. 13 Screenshot of PVsyst the main results and the simulation parameters

The pumps' sizes were somewhat different due to the limitations in PVsyst software, which only offers fixed sizes, however, the sizes were not too different. The selected pumps were Grundfos with 700 V nominal voltage and 86A nominal current.

PV power outputs and energy were changing every month. As shown in figure 14, the peak of power output happened in June, July, and August, while the least happened in January and December.

Fig. 14 Normalized productions (per installed kWp)

The possibility of having cloudy days are taken into account. For example, in January and July presented in Figs. 15 and 16 the results of the Algorithm for July clear that is the most critical month for the crops irrigation and the amount all the stored energy is consumed.

Fig. 15 Irradiation, array and pump energy over one day in January

Fig. 16 Irradiation , array and pump energy over one day in July

6.2. Results of Simulation

Fig. 17 The proposed system model in Simulink

The complete model of solar water pumping system which is based on Simulink is shown below in figure 17. Simulation results have shown that the output power is changing corresponding with the irradiation and temperature variation with the MPPT and boost converter as figure 18,19,20 and 21. Also, increasing in temperature directly affects the PV output as it goes down, while decreasing in temperature improves the performance of the PV array. Moreover, as figure 22 illustrates, the flow rate requirement which is the system output was being fulfilled.

Fig. 18 Simulation results of step irradiation PO MPPT (a) Solar Irradiation

Fig. 19 Simulation results of step irradiation PO MPPT (b) Terminal voltage of the array

Fig. 20 Simulation results of step irradiation PO MPPT (c) Terminal current of the array

Fig. 21 Simulation results of step irradiation PO MPPT (d) DC power output of the PV array

Fig. 22 Flow rate, 0.0166 m³/s

Fig. 23 Motor load speed, 1480 rpm.

7. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This study has shown dynamic modeling of a large scale solar powered water pumping system which is fed by 58 kW PV source. The system simulation has been investigated and carried out using Matlab/Simulink, thus, it shows satisfactory results. Dynamic results indicate that MPPT algorithm for DC-DC converter and controller are able to achieve the objective for a variation in the input temperature and input solar irradiance.

Moreover, the feasibility of using such system in Egypt is much higher than any elsewhere since there is an enormous solar resources available. Even though the study only focused on one location which is Wadi Elnatron which is a moderate spot, there are some regions in Egypt have higher total solar radiation such as southern area [10].

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